

therefore *one possible* reading of this sign in Ĝirsu texts is indeed **il**, the word **UN.ÍL** in these texts is *never* followed by **-la**. His example (footnote 60) would have been the *only* example, had it not been for Tohru Maeda, who collated the text which contains the passage quoted by Heimpel and which according to Maeda should be read **gurum₂ ak UN.ÍL-e-ne** (see *ASJ* 2 p. 205).

Remco DE MAAIJER (20-11-1999)

94) L'infixe directif /i/, /y/ – Dans *ELS*, j'ai admis que le préfixe local {e} « remplace » le préfixe [ix] {b + i} dans les cas où l'apparition de ce dernier est bloquée par la structure de la forme verbale : après les préf. III 'dimensionnels' et après {b + a} [...] (p. 240) et qu'il est, selon toute vraisemblance, étymologiquement identique à la postposition {e} et au préfixe III {i} (p. 246 et n. 625). Dans un article récent¹, G. Zólyomi a suggéré de voir dans /y/ (mon {e}) un allomorphe de /i/ après voyelle (p. 230). Quoique sans conséquence au niveau pratique, cette hypothèse est théoriquement importante, puisqu'elle propose un système plus élégant que le mien. Dans le cadre de cette note, je ne veux pas entrer dans les détails d'une argumentation complexe et – à mes yeux du moins – souvent spéculative, mais seulement attirer l'attention sur deux difficultés qui ne semblent pas avoir été prises en considération par l'auteur :

1. Contrairement à l'évolution /ay/ > /ē/, /uy/ ((-)Cu-u₃-, etc.) > /ē/ ((-)Ce-, etc.) est phonétiquement problématique.

2. Pour rendre compte du fait que les formes où /y/ est graphiquement explicité sont dans l'immense majorité des cas intransitives, Zólyomi admet que « if slot I is occupied by an FPP, the writing does not reflect the presence of any element » (p. 230). Indépendamment du fait qu'il est dangereux (à partir de l'époque d'Ur III) d'argumenter avec des absents, des formes **transitives** du type -a-B sont sporadiquement attestées ; un exemple particulièrement clair est M.C. Biga, SEL 3 (1986) 28-32 ii 21 sq., iii 25 et rev. iii 1 : (mu) PN dumu lugal-ke₄ šu-na ba-a-ge₄(-a-še₃) (cf. W. Heimpel, *BSA* 8 [1995] 106).

1. *Directive infix and oblique object in Sumerian : An account of the history of their relationship*, *Or.* 68 (1999) 215-253. Remarquer en passant que l'idée de regrouper sous le terme « datif {ra} et le loc.-term. {e} » (pp. 251-253) a été avancée pour la première fois par B. Jagersma dans une communication faite à Münster en 1995, dans le cadre du *Sumerian Grammar Discussion Group (Basic structure of a Sumerian sentence)*, handout pp. 7 sq., 4.4 « A note on the dative case ». Cf. surtout p. 7 : « The dative case as I see it incorporates two traditional Sumerological cases : the dative as well as the locative-terminative case. In my view, the forms commonly assigned to a locative-terminative case differ from the forms of the dative case only in being of a different gender class, while they do not represent a different case ».

Pascal ATTINGER (21-11-1999)

Seftigenstr. 42

CH-3007 BERNE (Suisse)

95) an-na zabar – In *ASJ* 19 (1997) : 53-62 B.R. Foster published YBC 12130, which he described as 'a Sumerian merchant's account of the Dilmun trade'. In addition to purchasing 975 minas of copper (**urudu**), DLU the merchant acquired 27.5 minas of **an-na zabar** (iii 2), which Foster translates as 'tin (in/for?) bronze' (p. 55). Foster notes (p. 56), 'The meaning of this expression remains uncertain. It may refer to a specific quality of tin or, less likely, to tin already present in bronze according to some unexpressed proportion' (cf. Limet, *JESHO* 15 [1972] : 14, n. 2).

Recently published lead-isotope analyses of late 3rd millennium metal artifacts from Tell Abraç in the United Arab Emirates by one of my students (see L. Weeks, *Antiquity* 73 [1999] : 49-64) have now shown that, in spite of availability of copper from the Oman mountain range, 'at least some of the bronze' found at the site 'was being traded to Tell Abraç in its alloyed form, either as ingots or as finished objects ... The evidence for the use of foreign bronze at the site is interesting, given analyses of Iron Age material from Oman which suggest that, at this time, bronze was produced by alloying imported tin with local copper' (p. 59).

The implication of these analyses is clear. Copper from the Oman ophiolite was not the source of the metal used in manufacturing the unusually high percentage of tin bronzes found at the site. Rather, there existed in the late 3rd millennium a trade in already alloyed bronze which reached the Oman peninsula.

I suggest that the **an-na zabar** acquired in Dilmun was precisely the same material in circulation further south at Tell Abraç. It was, as its Sumerian name literally reads, 'tin bronze', as distinct from refined copper or pure tin. Whether it was acquired in ingot, object or scrap form we cannot say. If it was in object form then it was most probably intended for melting and re-casting once it arrived back in Mesopotamia. The lead-isotope analyses of the material at Tell Abraç confirm, however, that ready made bronze circulated alongside copper and tin in the base metals market of the third millennium B.C.

D.T. POTTS (2-12-1999)

School of Archaeology, University of Sydney
2006 NEW SOUTH WALES (Australie)